

P O L I C Y B R I E F

DR. NHLANHLA HLONGWA | JUNE 2025

Can South Africa's Water Systems Overcome the Threat of Emerging Contaminants?

Executive summary

Although they are essential for general development, industrialisation and agricultural expansion, while essential for general development, are indirectly impacting the environment in a negative way. These impacts include harm to human health, disruption of aquatic life systems, and long-term environmental degradation. What's even more concerning is that across the globe, water pollution and wastage have reached critical levels globally, threatening freshwater sustainability, which is essential for socioeconomic development. Emerging contaminants (ECs) often occur naturally in water sources and their ecosystems, which pose a threat to aquatic life systems. While these ECs may harm human health, the risks to aquatic ecosystems are even greater. Notably, ECs often enter the aquatic environment through numerous pathways, including municipal and industrial water waste treatment plants (WWTPs), hospitals, sewer overflows, sewer leakages, and agricultural surface runoff. Again, inefficiencies in waste water treatment processes at WWTPs are an ongoing issue. Given the increasing confirmation and evidence of water contamination and pollution, South Africa's water systems are impacting public health, ecosystems, and water security, and therefore the conception and implementation of inclusive interventions are essential. In the light of the above challenges, this brief seeks to underscore the following actionable strategies and solutions:

- Cs, including antiretrovirals, pesticides, and industrial chemicals, present challenges due to the lack of advanced technologies needed to adequately remove these complex pollutants from current wastewater treatment systems, which poses risks to human health and aquatic life.
- Establishing a national EC monitoring framework is essential for effective water resource management and alignment with National Development Plan (NDP) 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). Upgrading wastewater treatment with hybrid approaches, for example, combining Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP) and nature-based solutions (NbSs), such as biofiltration with biochar media, can effectively reduce EC concentrations, offering a cost-effective, eco-friendly way to mitigate ecological and public health risks.
- Investment into the development and deployment of efficient waste disposal technologies is vital, as well as improving access into the appropriate sanitation services, including curbing illegal domestic and industrial waste disposal.
- Immediate and coordinated policy actions are required to safeguard South Africa's water systems from irreversible damage.

Introduction

South Africa faces a growing water crisis, including scarcity and oversupply in some areas. This water crisis is intensified by factors such as climate change, urbanisation, and population growth¹. Compounding this issue is the increasing presence of ECs in surface water, groundwater, and wastewater, partly as a consequence of their ineffective removal by current wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)^{2,6}. This policy brief aims to propose actionable strategies for mitigating the risks of ECs in South Africa's water systems through improved monitoring, infrastructure upgrades, and regulatory reforms.

Critique of the policy context

Even though South Africa has policy frameworks in place, such as the National Environmental Management Act (NEMA), that address broad environmental governance, including pollution control, sustainable development, and environmental impact assessments, there is no cohesive regulatory framework specifically addressing ECs⁷. Comparatively, international initiatives provide valuable lessons³. The European Union's Water Framework Directive (WFD), established in 2000, mandates stringent monitoring and management of ECs, including the identification and control of substances, such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)⁴. The implementation of this comprehensive framework has resulted in significantly reduced pollutant levels in European water systems by aligning member states on targeted actions. Similarly, Canada's Federal Contaminated Sites Action Plan (FCSAP), initiated in 2005, focuses on upgrading wastewater treatment facilities to remove ECs. Investments in water treatment technologies have proven effective in eliminating pharmaceuticals and personal care products from effluents, thereby protecting aquatic environments⁵.

These initiatives highlight the importance of robust policy frameworks and technological advancements in managing ECs, demonstrating clear pathways to safeguard water quality and public health. South Africa can draw from these models to develop a cohesive regulatory framework, enhance monitoring, and prioritise infrastructure upgrades. Addressing these gaps requires the coordinated efforts of government, the private sector, and communities. Each stakeholder group has a critical role to play in ensuring South Africa's water systems are protected and sustainable. Each stakeholder and the role they play is outlined as follows:

Government

- Develop and enforce a cohesive regulatory framework for ECs, aligning with the NDP 2030 and global water quality

objectives, including SDGs, such as SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation, SDG 14: Life Below Water, and SDG 15: Life on Land.

- Implement a centralised EC tracking system to ensure data-driven decision-making and transparency.

Private sector

- Promote partnerships with government and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and research organisations to introduce and build capacity in green technologies and NbSs for EC removal.
- Adhere to regulatory standards and investing in research for cost-effective EC mitigation strategies.

Communities

- Encourage participation in campaigns on the proper disposal of harmful substances to reduce EC introduction into water systems.
- Engage in citizen science programmes to provide regional insights, especially in areas with limited government oversight.
- Adopt sustainable practices and advocate cleaner water policies

Research method and approach

This policy brief emerges from an in-depth analysis of existing data sources, such as strategies, annual progress reports, other official publications of the relevant entities, and respective policies and strategies.

Results and policy implications

Research indicates the widespread occurrence of ECs, including pharmaceuticals, including antiretrovirals, such as Nevirapine and Lamivudine, pesticides, such as Atrazine, Terbutylazine, and industrial chemicals, across South Africa's water systems¹. As shown in Figure 1, high concentrations of ECs are reported in surface waters in regions, such as KwaZulu-Natal and the Free State, with specific contaminants, such as fluoroquinolones and Atenolol exceeding safe levels. Gauteng and Limpopo Provinces also show notable EC presence, though levels are lower compared to other high-risk areas. Risk quotient analyses confirm significant ecological risks, with 12 of the 32 contaminants detected at concentrations that pose hazards to aquatic life and public health. WWTPs across South Africa are currently inadequately equipped to manage these pollutants, resulting in their discharge into critical water systems. Without prompt intervention, EC pollution will continue to endanger biodiversity, water security, and public health.

Figure 1: Concentration of selected ECs in surface water

Source: Gani et al., 2021

Health and environmental risks of key ECs detected in water sources

1. Fluoroquinolones

- Fluoroquinolones are persistent antibiotics that contribute to antibiotic resistance in aquatic organisms, leading to reduced biodiversity and altered microbial communities in water ecosystems. They can disrupt the normal growth and reproductive cycles of fish and aquatic invertebrates.
- High levels of fluoroquinolones can also cause skin reactions, gastrointestinal issues, and, in severe cases, neurological and musculoskeletal effects if ingested over time.

2. Antiretroviral drugs

- Antiretroviral drugs, such as nevirapine, efavirenz, and lamivudine, can disrupt hormone regulation in fish and amphibians, affecting reproductive systems and causing abnormal development. Persistent exposure can lead to bioaccumulation in aquatic species, posing long-term risks to the food chain.
- Although critical for human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) treatment, antiretrovirals in water at sub-therapeutic levels can cause liver toxicity over time. Additionally, their environmental persistence raises concerns about the development of drug resistance.

3. Pesticides

- Atrazine, a known endocrine disruptor, causes reproductive abnormalities in amphibians and fish, such as the feminisation of male frogs. Pesticides also reduce survival rates in aquatic organisms, especially affecting early developmental stages of fish and amphibians.
- Atrazine exposure in humans is linked to hormonal disruptions, potentially increasing risks for reproductive health issues and certain cancers. Long-term exposure to pesticide-contaminated water can affect child development and cardiovascular health.

4. Common pharmaceuticals in water systems

- Though less toxic, high concentrations of caffeine and aspirin can interfere with normal behaviours and metabolism in aquatic organisms. Beta-blocker medication, such as Atenolol, has been shown to impact heart rates and stress responses in fish, leading to impaired mobility and reproductive issues.
- Chronic exposure to caffeine and pharmaceuticals in drinking water could contribute to cumulative health effects, particularly in sensitive groups like pregnant women and children. Atenolol might also affect individuals with cardiovascular sensitivities or interact with other medications.

Policy recommendations

Implementing the proposed measures, such as upgrading wastewater treatment infrastructure, establishing a national monitoring framework, and enforcing regulatory reforms, has the potential to significantly reduce EC concentrations in water systems. These actions will enhance water security, protect biodiversity, and align South Africa with global water quality standards, ensuring sustainable access to clean water for all.

To ensure the effectiveness of these actions, a phased implementation roadmap is recommended. This process will require a dedicated task force comprising key stakeholders from government, the private sector, and academic institutions, with the establishment of a central regulatory authority for EC monitoring being a critical component. Securing funding through public-private partnerships and international grants will be essential, and a detailed cost-benefit analysis should be conducted to ensure that resources are allocated efficiently and sustainably. The following phased plan is recommended:

- 2024–2025: Launch a pilot national monitoring programme in high-risk provinces, focusing on regions with the highest EC concentrations, such as KwaZulu-Natal and Free State.
- 2026–2028: Initiate a phased programme of infrastructure upgrades for WWTPs, prioritising urban centres with the most critical contamination issues.
- 2029–2030: Achieve compliance with the SDG and NDP targets for water safety by ensuring that all WWTPs meet EC removal standards.

According to an SABC News report on 31 March 2025, researchers from the University of Johannesburg (UJ) recently revealed that high toxicity levels (pollution and contamination) in the river systems are primarily caused by human activities. They found cancer-causing chemicals in the Klip River in Gauteng, which is a serious concern for public health. Besides the fact that consuming this polluted, contaminated water affects poor communities, it has the poten-

tial to significantly disrupt ecosystems and aquatic life. As UJ experts recently recommended, there is no substitute for investment into ongoing research and monitoring of river systems, which will help to direct and guide stricter enforcement of environmental laws and regulations. Furthermore, continuous national research and monitoring will generate consistent, reliable data. Tracing and tracking water pollution trends play a crucial role in informing and adapting public policy. This approach would enable governmental agencies to effectively implement the integrated water preservation and conservation strategies, ensuring water security, and promoting broader environmental sustainability.

Conclusion

In addition to broader sanitation efforts and enhanced compliance monitoring systems for industrial, environmental, and agricultural activities, including surface water, groundwater and wastewater, there is an urgent need to address inefficiencies in WWTPs. The issues associated with the WWTPs highlight the need to improve infrastructure, particularly in rural and densely populated areas. Rapid population growth in these areas increases pressure on municipal and industrial waste water systems in water treatment plants. Addressing these issues involves investing in the water infrastructure and should support the review and adoption of treatment procedures, as well as protocols for optimum efficiency to achieve sustainable water management and safeguard public and environmental health.

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Author

- **Nhlanhla Hlongwa,**
PhD; Post doctoral fellow researcher, Future Water Institute, University of Cape and National Research Foundation, Business Advancement: Impact of Partnerships
- Enquiries to: Dr. Nhlanhla Hlongwa: N.Hlongwa@nrf.ac.za

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